

Estimating the Impact of Soft Errors on AI-based Perception in Automotive

Shailesh Sudhakara Hegde, Dinesh Cyril Selvaraj, Josie E. Rodriguez Condia,
Nicola Amati, Carla Fabiana Chiasserini, Francesco Paolo Deflorio, Matteo Sonza Reorda
Politecnico di Torino - Center for Automotive Research and Sustainable Mobility (CARS)

Abstract—Artificial intelligence (AI) is boosting the development of complex functionalities in the automotive domain, paving the way for autonomous decision-making capabilities of vehicles. However, integrating such complex functionalities at the system level is challenging due to the short time to market with limited development, verification, and validation periods. Moreover, automotive applications require compliance with strict safety regulations, which demands effective strategies to ensure timely development while allowing thorough dependability evaluations. This work addresses the system-level reliability of automotive applications by proposing a strategy named *TIARA* (Two-step Integrated Reliability Assessment) to assess the impact of hardware faults (modeled as soft errors) on AI-based perception tasks. Our strategy allows for the exploration and evaluation of algorithms, driving controllers, and critical operational scenarios, considering the effects of faults affecting the hardware up to the vehicle level. To tame the huge computational complexity, *TIARA* first exploits a static analysis to estimate the fault vulnerabilities and identifies the most critical code blocks. Then, the most critical application blocks (susceptible to faults from hardware) are targeted to evaluate the fault’s impact on the vehicle dynamics and determine their effect at the system level, combining perception, control, and driving features. Our experimental results, obtained on a test case corresponding to a *Lane Centering Assistance* application based on the *YoloP* model and under different driving scenarios, show the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Index Terms—Automotive, Artificial intelligence, Lane Keeping / Lane Centering Assistance, Reliability evaluation, Soft errors

I. INTRODUCTION

Functional safety and reliability are primary concerns in developing new *Autonomous and Semi-Autonomous Driving systems* (AD&SAD) and they are becoming even more important as vehicles get equipped with increasingly sophisticated electronic devices to enhance driving capabilities, user comfort, and system autonomy [1]. Furthermore, additional concerns are emerging about using new technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) in such safety-critical scenarios.

Indeed, AI algorithms (e.g., *deep Convolutional Neural Networks* or CNNs) have been widely adopted to enable complex tasks, such as object recognition and sensor fusion, which are pivotal to the control and system management in *Advanced Driving Assistance Systems* (ADAS) [2], [3]. Due to their operational complexity, AI applications often require high computational power and data-intensive operations, which need to be handled by advanced hardware accelerators with extended capabilities, such as embedded *Neural Processing Units* (NPU), *Tensor Processing Units* (TPUs), or *Graphics Processing Units*

(GPUs) [4]–[6]. Both features (high computational power and data-intensive operations) in AI applications increase the challenges in assessing their reliability and guaranteeing the correct system operation during the in-field operation. Furthermore, AI in automotive must satisfy industry dependability requirements (i.e., ISO 26262/22989 [7], [8]) to avoid most threats and hazards (e.g., bugs and unstable corruption states), which also involves the clever adaptation of traditional strategies to evaluate AI applications reliability [9]. In particular, the development, the design exploration, and the early reliability estimation of these systems against faults in hardware usually require considerable engineering effort, leading to long development times, from unit design to system verification [5]. Thus, frameworks and early development environments are crucial to efficiently integrate and evaluate design and reliability parameters in AI systems (e.g., sensor fusion and driving agents) and to support effective design improvements.

State of the art and existing gaps. Several works introduced strategies for developing, verifying, and validating applications in automotive, which are commonly automated by supporting frameworks that can be classified into three categories: *i*) software-based simulators, *ii*) hybrid (software and hardware) systems, and *iii*) hardware emulation systems.

Software simulation frameworks are flexible environments that allow easy integration of several system components (e.g., controllers, in-vehicle networks, and sensing features) with reasonable fidelity of the operational environment (e.g., physics and realistic scenarios) and provide mechanisms to evaluate, analyze, and simulate the interaction of the different automotive system components. Moreover, these frameworks can interact with each other, as well as with users (e.g., through augmented reality [10]), and are flexible enough to update and deploy system configurations with minimal effort [11]. In [12], the authors introduced a functional verification and validation simulator for algorithms and solutions for connected AD&SAD systems. However, the framework can only assess operational features, not dependability or reliability. Resiliency characterization features have instead been addressed in, e.g., [13], which presents a fault injection framework (*AVFI*) for the holistic evaluation of traffic violations due to faults/errors in AD&SAD components (lidar/camera sensors, communicating paths, actuators, and AI-based perception, localization, and motion planning). The framework combines an autonomous driving simulator (*CARLA*) [14] with an AI-based AD Agent.

Unfortunately, scenario generators, such as *CARLA*, *IsaacSim*, or *Open Pilot* often oversimplify the dynamics of AD systems, and their limited sensor support may lead to an inaccurate representation of the behavior of modern AD systems.

The second strategy (*hybrid*) combines hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) solutions and software frameworks for the analysis of AD&SAD systems. By simulating components, such as vehicular traffic scenarios and the behavior of some system elements, it enables the pseudo-real-/real-time evaluation and verification of system functional properties [15]–[17]. Unfortunately, these solutions involve costly testbed facilities (e.g., vehicles in controlled environments) and specialized instrumentation, equipment, and custom frameworks, thus typically exhibiting high complexity and lack of flexibility [18], [19].

The third strategy (hardware emulation or HIL evaluations) combines real components (e.g., engines, actuators, sensors, board computers) with early-stage designs and solutions to verify and validate their real-time operation and evaluate functional features in AD&SAD systems. This strategy also involves specialized testbed and instrumentation facilities for real-time (in-the-loop) system evaluation. As a result, at the hardware and system levels, resilience evaluation is constrained by the few fault models that can be evaluated in an AD&SAD system (e.g., interconnect failures or system perturbations). In this context, [20] describes an emulator using FPGAs for the early codesign and functional verification of software and hardware components for automotive, which, however, neglects resilience assessment and analysis.

In conclusion, the following scientific and technical gaps still exist. *First*, most existing strategies and frameworks for AD&SAD systems focus on verifying and evaluating functional system properties, while neglecting reliability. *Second*, the few approaches focusing on evaluating the resilience of AI-based software and hardware components require elaborated frameworks, which often can not evaluate the reliability of AI applications (e.g., perception) on realistic traffic/road scenarios. *Third*, existing works have overlooked crucial aspects, namely, the impact of hardware faults on AD&SAD systems and their evaluation at the system level via the adoption of relevant metrics, such as users’ vehicle ride comfort.

Our approach. To address the existing gaps, we define a new strategy for the early-stage design exploration and reliability assessment of AI-based applications for automotive systems. Our methodology, which we named *TIARA* (*Two-step IntegrAted Reliability Assessment*), consists of a two-step approach: *Static analysis* and *Dynamic evaluation*. The static analysis focuses on identifying the most vulnerable parts (e.g., CNN layers) of an AI-based application used in an AD&SAD system resorting to a detailed pseudo-exhaustive fault injection campaign [21], [22] working on static images. In this way, we can identify which stages of the AI software are the most relevant for the application to provide a correct output. Then, the dynamic analysis is conducted through statistical fault campaigns focusing only on the most vulnerable layers and characterizing the corruptions induced by faults in the hardware on the closed-loop system and the vehicle dynamics.

Fig. 1. Example of a scenario targeted by our prototype, corresponding to a car moving in a winding scenario. On the right, the fault-free and the faulty car trajectory (Traj.).

Thanks to this approach, the TIARA methodology was demonstrated to be highly efficient and able to effectively trade off accuracy and computational effort.

To practically validate the proposed approach we developed a custom and flexible framework that integrates an automotive-grade traffic/road scenario simulator (*AVS SCANer*), sensor models, vehicle dynamics, and driving agents in the loop, to evaluate the reliability of the whole closed-loop system.

In our experiments, we considered, as a use case, a *Lane Keeping Assistance* application (i.e., *Lane Centering Assistance* or *LCA*), which aims at holding a vehicle centered in the lane [23]. In detail, the evaluation focuses on the AI software for perception (based on the *YoloP* Neural Network for lane center detection) under three representative driving scenarios (*straight*, *winding*, and *with obstacle*). Our results from the static analysis indicate that the most vulnerable layers in the AI software are the *YoloP Backbone* and *Head* parts: faults affecting them can significantly impact the system detection tasks. Then, the dynamic evaluation demonstrates that road/traffic features can impact the overall system reliability when faults arise in perception and might lead to vehicle collision or lateral deviations, as depicted in Fig. 1.

Our contributions. In summary, we provide the following main contributions:

- We introduce the TIARA methodology comprising two steps (*Static* and *Dynamic*) to enable the early reliability estimation of AI software in automotive systems. The *Static* step identifies the most susceptible layers of the AI software, while the *Dynamic* evaluation focuses only on the most vulnerable parts of the AI software. In this way, TIARA can provide an accurate but computationally feasible closed-loop system evaluation.
- By applying TIARA, we performed an exhaustive soft error characterization of the *YoloP model* for perception (road lane detection) by injecting more than 8,599,789 errors (bit-flips) in the weights. The results indicate that around 1.3% of the fault sources in the *Backbone* and *Head* layers can critically impact the perception task. TIARA also proved to be able to rank different scenarios according to their criticality, allowing to select the most suitable ones for reliability assessment.

In the following, Sec. III provides a background of the primary functional safety and reliability features in automotive, besides overviewing AI-based perception tasks and the *YoloP*

architecture. Sec. III introduces the TIARA methodology, while Sec. IV describes the experimental setup. Sec. V presents and discusses the experimental results. Finally, Sec. VI concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Safety and reliability threats in perception systems

Nowadays, the semiconductor’s miniaturization supports the design and integration of high-performance systems, which is crucial for efficiently deploying AI algorithms in many domains, including automotive. New devices (e.g., below 14 nm) are, however, highly vulnerable to faults from temporal and environmental variations arising during the in-field operation (e.g., *premature aging* or *external radiation*), which may substantially impact the system resilience [24]. Furthermore, new applications used in automotive (e.g., AI-based perception tasks, as depicted in Fig. 2(a)) involve the use of multi-sensor platforms (e.g., Camera, Lidar, radar, ultrasonic, or GPS) and control systems, which may also be subject to faults. These factors make evaluating the resiliency and reliability of an automotive system a particularly challenging task, also considering the strict safety and reliability requirements specified by automotive standards like ISO 26262/22989.

As a consequence, the vulnerability of automotive systems to faults from their underlying hardware (e.g., CPUs, GPUs) and to errors in the running AI application is still far from being fully understood [16]. The performance degradation due to faults may vary significantly depending on the system configuration, AI algorithm, and the adopted fault/error models (e.g., permanent/transient faults, such as Gaussian noise, occlusion, or bit-flips). This further exacerbates the need for efficient system evaluation techniques, during design phases, to support the development of countermeasures or design improvements.

B. Automotive perception with YoloP

AI algorithms have largely overcome the performance and development speed of manually tuned solutions. They represent by far the most preferred solutions for computer vision tasks since AI algorithms can effectively process multi-modal data collected through multiple sensors and realize obstacle and environment perception for AD&SAD applications [25].

The YoloP [26] (*You Only Look Once for Panoptic driving perception*) is a real-time, multi-task AI framework designed to simultaneously perform object detection, drivable area segmentation, and lane line detection for driving environments. Its architecture comprises three main stages: 1) **Backbone**, 2) **Neck**, and 3) **Head**, as depicted in Fig. 2(b). The **Backbone** extracts multi-scale features from input images, using a deep CNN based on the YOLO architecture. Moreover, it is optimized for handling diverse perception tasks concurrently. The **Neck** stage refines and enriches features across different layers, enhancing the ability to detect varying-size objects through *Spatial Pyramid Pooling* (SPP) layers. Finally, the **Head** uses independent heads per task: one for object detection inside the driving scene, such as vehicles, pedestrians, and traffic signs (*Detection*), one for drivable areas on the road

Fig. 2. General scheme of AD&SAD systems (a); the YoloP architecture (b).

(*Drivable Area Segmentation*), and one for lane boundaries (*Lane Line Detection*). The clever organization of the YoloP architecture enables the reuse of some layers (those in the **Backbone** and **Neck**) to process several features while using individual heads for specific perception/identification tasks.

In this work, we characterize one of the critical use cases in automotive perception, namely, LCA, and the impacts of faults on the LCA system performance. The results aim to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed reliability assessment methodology.

III. THE TIARA STRATEGY

Our strategy, named TIARA, faces the challenges of characterizing and identifying the most vulnerable structures and scenarios in AI-based applications for AD&SAD systems by using a methodology that consists of two steps: *i*) Static analysis and *ii*) Dynamic evaluation, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The first step (*static*) performs a pseudo-exhaustive error evaluation to identify the most susceptible code blocks in the AI application under operational scenarios. Then, the second step (*Dynamic*) focuses on the identified vulnerable code blocks to evaluate fault impacts in the AI application and their effects at the vehicle level, working with a closed-loop approach (i.e., including scenario, sensors, perception, and control agents). Importantly, our strategy allows us to efficiently cope with the inherent complexity of evaluating data-intensive and computationally dense AI applications running in a very complex system, making it possible to characterize the application’s behavior in different scenarios and the presence of faults. Our approach thus successfully supports the early estimation of vulnerabilities during system development to identify further design improvements.

First, we identify the system and the code structures in a targeted AI application (e.g., LCA) and define those code parts of direct interest, i.e., layers inside a multi-class machine learning application actively executing a targeted task, such as perception or control. In addition, it is crucial to identify the critical driving situations for system evaluation (e.g., weather

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the proposed TIARA strategy for assessing the reliability of AI-based applications in automotive.

conditions, vehicle speed, traffic levels, number of pedestrians, and sensing devices).

In the following, we detail the proposed TIARA strategy.

A. Static evaluation of the AI-powered application

This step evaluates and characterizes the impact of faults on the code structure of the AI application only. In particular, pseudo-exhaustive fault injection campaigns are performed on the AI application by injecting soft errors in the weights, output feature maps, or a combination of both. Our environment supports the injection of both permanent and transient faults in the underlying hardware [27], [28]. This evaluation uses limited, highly representative input stimuli, e.g., data frames from crucial driving situations.

The collected output effects are analyzed to correlate corruptions with the internal application structures (e.g., neurons or layers). In detail, we classify errors according to their impact on the AI application outputs as: *Silent Data Corruptions* (SDCs), when an error causes a mismatch in the application’s operation (e.g., false pedestrian detection or incorrect lane detection), *Detected Unrecoverable Errors* (DUEs), when an error collapses or hangs the application, and *Masked* for benign errors with no impact on the application outputs. Then, those application structures, which are identified as the most vulnerable (*‘highly sensitive’*), are the primary candidates for the dynamic (closed-loop) evaluation of the system.

B. Dynamic reliability assessment

In this step, we extend the analysis by introducing a vehicle model that integrates the AI application for navigation purposes in simulated dynamic urban scenarios. An automotive-grade scenario generator builds scenarios that include surrounding vehicle movements, varying traffic conditions, and sensing device interaction (e.g., cameras, LiDAR) in the vehicle with AI applications for perception or control. The evaluation of the AI application is based on the closed-loop operation of the system that captures real-time environmental data (e.g., lane markings) using camera sensors (i.e., the sequence of scenario frames), as depicted in Fig. 3 (bottom). Then, the data is processed by the AI application to detect

features of interest, such as estimating the lane center. Based on the collected features, the vehicle’s control logic adjusts its movements to navigate the road environment effectively.

For the evaluation, a preliminary fault-free simulation evaluates the AI application’s effectiveness in navigating a specific driving condition, establishing a baseline for system operation. Then, several statistical fault injection campaigns [9] characterize the system under dynamic and changing driving conditions by injecting errors into the AI application’s highly susceptible code structures (e.g., layers), previously identified during the static analysis. The AI application’s assessment aims to determine the impact of corruption and propagation on the closed-loop system. Specifically, a custom framework that integrates the scenario generator automatically evaluates the system under several typical and critical maneuvers and traffic scenarios when a fault is injected.

The impact of faults injected into the AI application (within the closed-loop system) is evaluated based on vehicle performance metrics. For instance, in LCA, we evaluate lane deviation, steering command, and lateral acceleration metrics. Similarly, an *Adaptive Cruise Control* (ACC) application focuses on collision rates and maintaining safe following distances.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To automate the evaluation process, we developed a custom and flexible software framework in *Python* orchestrating the different steps implemented by the environment.

The static analysis framework integrates a custom software fault injector with extended injection capabilities (based on *PytorchFI* [29]) to evaluate transient faults (e.g., bit-flips) in the weights and feature maps of the AI application. Moreover, the dynamic evaluation framework also incorporates an automotive-grade realistic virtual scenario generator (*SCANeR* by *AVSimulation*), sensors, vehicle dynamics, driving controller agents, and image processing components (based on *OpenCV*) to assess closed-loop system reliability. In particular, *SCANeR* is a comprehensive platform designed to develop and verify ADAS and AD&SAD technologies. This tool allows the study of the behavior of a complete vehicle moving in real-world driving scenarios by supporting high-fidelity sensor simulation, realistic vehicle dynamics, and accurate environmental conditions. Fig. 4 depicts the *SCANeR* architecture, showcasing module interactions and the ability to include custom modules for the TIARA strategy integration. In detail, the custom modules (shown at the bottom-right) integrate the modules describing the IA application, the fault injector, complementary processing tasks, and the controller.

As a study case, we configured the framework to evaluate the impact of faults in the LCA application that uses YoloP for perception. Then, we configured *SCANeR* to evaluate three typical traffic scenarios, namely, *straight* (S), *winding* (W), and *with obstacle* (O), in a 3-lane highway with intermittent line marking and with daylight conditions. Each traffic scenario includes a target actor and one external actor (car) moving at 12 km/h for an evaluation period of 23 s. The S and W scenarios place the actor at varying distances during the evaluation. In

Fig. 4. Overview of the SCANeR architecture.

contrast, the \circ scenario consists of a straight road with the external actor changing line (approaching from the right) after 2 s from the start of the evaluation. Furthermore, we tune up the YoloP application to process 20 frames/s, considering one (1280×720 pixels) camera mounted on the front of the vehicle as input for the LCA task. In all experiments, the target actor uses a proportional controller for ACC.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents and discusses the results of the static analysis and dynamic evaluation of the automotive system.

Using the static analysis, we identified the most vulnerable code blocks (layers) by exhaustively injecting 8,599,789 soft errors (bit-flips) in all the weights of YoloP structures (*Backbone*, *Neck*, and *Head*). Then, the dynamic evaluation characterized the impact of the errors on the driving system by injecting 3,000 random soft errors only in the most susceptible layers (1,000 per scenario) with an interval of confidence of 95% and 1% error margin. Each soft error is placed before the application’s execution. The experiments required 359 h (343 h for the static and 16 h for the dynamic ones).

To speed up the static analysis experiments, we deployed the framework on a 6-node cluster with 2 Intel 16-core Xeon Scalable Processors Gold 6130 (2.10 GHz) and equipped with 6 NVIDIA Tesla V100 SXM2 and 32 GB of RAM. The dynamic evaluation used a workstation with an 8-core Intel i7-11700K (3.6 GHz) processors, 32 GB of RAM, and one NVIDIA Geforce RTX3080_{Ti} GPU with 12 GB of RAM.

A. Static analysis of the AI-based perception application

The static analysis identifies the fault effects on YoloP outputs by examining the magnitude of the produced errors on the lane center for each scenario. Then, the analysis determines the application’s most susceptible code blocks (*layers*).

Fig. 5 reports the maximum distance between the vehicle’s center and the lane center from faults impacting the AI task’s layers on all analyzed scenarios. The vertical axis represents the median, quartiles (Q1 and Q3), and variability, providing insights into the distribution of lane center offsets. In general, the most susceptible layers in YoloP (*those causing the largest lane center deviations*) are consistent for all analyzed scenarios and are located in the *Backbone* (layers 0–7), parts of the *Neck* (layers 8–14), and the *Head* (layers 34–42). Furthermore, some

Fig. 5. Distribution of the lane center offset errors on the layers of YoloP for the straight (S), winding (W), and with obstacle (O) traffic scenarios.

layers (34, 36, and 40) are highly prone to causing large offset deviations for most scenarios. In addition, during our analysis, we observed the intrinsic fault tolerance of some layers in the *Neck* of YoloP (layers 15–33 not shown in Fig. 5), as soft errors did not cause any corruption in the considered scenarios.

Interestingly, the results indicate that the maximum error deviation directly depends on the characteristics of the analyzed scenario (i.e., error magnitudes up to 0.041 m for S , 0.50 m for W , and up to 1.30 m for O). Moreover, a detailed analysis of the most critical error effects (large deviation magnitude) by evaluating the top 5% of the critical errors indicates that *Backbone* layers (near the input) are more sensitive in W and O scenarios. In contrast, the *Head* layers are more prone to errors in the S scenario. The most susceptible layers are the primary injection targets during the dynamic evaluation.

B. Dynamic evaluation

In this step, we analyzed the propagation of fault effects in perception and their impact on the car behavior by computing two metrics associated with the vehicle’s driving performance: the *i) Lateral Acceleration* (LACC) and the *ii) Steering Angle* (SA). Fig. 6 reports the distribution of the fault effects on LACC and SA for the three dynamic scenarios classified according to three severity levels: *low* (L), *medium* (M), and *high* (H) for the LACC (L ($< 1.5 \text{ m/s}^2$), M (between 1.5 and 3.0 m/s^2), and H ($> 3.0 \text{ m/s}^2$)) and the SA (L ($< 0.385 \text{ rad}$), M (between 0.385 and 1.181 rad), and H ($> 1.181 \text{ rad}$)).

The results show that some driving scenarios are more critical than others when the perception structure is faulty. For instance, the O scenario is up to $5\times$ more sensitive to faults than the others; hence, it is more likely to produce large deviations in LACC and SA than the S scenario. Similarly, the perception system is highly vulnerable to faults that occur in the W scenario, causing significant SA variations (i.e., around 60% of the injected faults produce effects of H severity).

Regarding the error sources, the results for both driving metrics indicate that faults in the *Head* layers (from 1% to 62%) are highly critical and can severely corrupt the system independently from the driving condition (Fig. 7), making them suitable candidates for design improvements or harden-

Fig. 6. Distribution of system severity impacts on the lateral acceleration (a) and steering angle (b), from faults in the *Backbone*, *Neck*, and *Head* of the perception task, for the three dynamic scenarios (S, W, O).

ing mechanisms. In contrast, some faults in the *Backbone* and *Neck* might be masked by the interaction of the controlling agent and the implicit resilience of the closed-loop system.

It is worth noting that the reliability evaluation of the LCA application with the proposed methodology, is intended to demonstrate the approach feasibility and its use for the early estimation and analysis of automotive applications under critical and corner traffic/road operative cases.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a method to analyze the reliability features of AI-based applications in automotive, studying the effects of hardware faults at the system (i.e., vehicle) level. Our method takes advantage of a two-step process. The first estimates the most vulnerable layers in the AI-based applications using pseudo-exhaustive fault injection campaigns. The second one performs statistical fault injection campaigns focusing only on the faults affecting the most vulnerable layers, allowing the evaluation of their effect on the vehicle behavior under different scenarios. Experimental results on a Lane Centering Assistance application and targeting the analysis of a perception task indicate that our strategy effectively identifies the most susceptible layers (those in the *Backbone* and *Lane Segmentation Head*). Also, they demonstrate that faults affecting AI-based perception might cause critical corruption in the overall system (up to 4.8% of large lateral acceleration deviations and up to 62% of steering angle corruptions). We emphasize that the proposed method allows the evaluation of several traffic/road scenarios with minimal configuration changes, and it is intended to provide early-stage reliability estimation of the system components.

Future work will extend the analysis to other system components, additional fault models, and critical traffic scenarios. We plan to combine our framework with HW-in-the-loop tools to evaluate the system's resilience and level of comfort.

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